

Feasibility Study of Creating Spaces for Cultural Tourism under the Floating Market Concept at Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand

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Abstract:- One of the popular cultural tourism and used as a tool to create added value in tourism. As well as being an important tool in the conservation of community-based cultural tourism, that is a floating market tour. This form of tourism is a form of community-based tourism management in Thailand that has received interest from both Thai and foreign tourists from the past to the present for not less than 40 years. Foreign tourists express their views on floating market tourism as a place to study Thai lifestyles. Most of the floating markets in Thailand are currently managed in the form of applying the concept of creating spaces for cultural tourism by creating a new floating market, but the cultural context of the local community's way of life. Keep the culture alive and easy to be touched and perceived by tourists under the use of cultural asset as a selling point for tourism, and the main aim of creating economic added value for the community and as a tool for cultural preservation clearly empirical new approach.

The main research objective is shown to study the feasibility of creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand. Data collected from 400 local residents which have gained residents surrounding the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand by purposive sampling technique.

The findings reported that the local residents which have gained residents surrounding the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand agreed with the creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon have cultural tourism capacities the overall average as whole as 3 aspects consists of (a) Tourism attraction potential aspect, (b) Tourism support potential aspect, and (c) Management aspect at a moderate level. But Compare the rule of three in arithmetic of the local residents' opinion level analysis to test the feasibility of creating spaces for cultural tourism under the floating market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand. Which is shown that Infeasibility of creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand.

Keywords:- Feasibility Study, Space Tourism, Floating Market, Cultural tourism, Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand

I. INTRODUCTION

Thailand has a diverse and unique culture in each locality, which is a tourist attraction, but the opening of cultural spaces as tourist attractions ignorantly or lack of good management causes cultural values and cultural landscape to change. Which may affect tourism establishing a clear framework or criteria for tourist quality standards for agencies and those involved in the care of tourist attractions can be used as a guideline for the development of tourist attractions, and as a tool to check tourist attractions standards to upgrade tourist attractions.[1] Therefore, it is important for sustainable tourism management and can be used as an indication to tourists about the quality of tourist attractions. As well as increasing the standards of Thailand's tourist attractions to be accepted both domestically and internationally in the near future.

One of the popular cultural tourism and used as a tool to create added value in tourism. As well as being an important tool in the conservation of community-based cultural tourism, that is a floating market tour. This form of tourism is a form of community-based tourism management in Thailand that has received interest from both Thai and foreign tourists from the past to the present for not less than 40 years. Foreign tourists express their views on floating market tourism as a place to study Thai lifestyles. And it is a strange and wonderful thing. Maybe because the floating market of Thailand is unique, showing the culture and way of life of the people in the old days such as traditions, dress, food, desserts, handicrafts, plays, performances and Thai music and so on. Not only that, a visit to the floating market can also empirically show the evolution of the traditional Thai lifestyle in the way of life of contemporary Thai people in the present. Most of the floating markets in Thailand are currently managed in the form of applying the concept of creating spaces for cultural tourism by creating a new floating market, but the cultural context of the local community's way of life. Keep the culture alive and easy to be touched and perceived by tourists under the use of cultural asset as a selling point for tourism, which is based on the concept of the common features of cultural tourism attraction consisted of 5 features: (a) Tell a story, (b) Make the

asset come live, (c) Make the experience participatory, (d) Make the experience relevant to the tourist, and (e) Focus on quality and authenticity. The five cultural characteristics in the text above have now been expanded and further enhanced in the form of creating spaces for cultural tourism with the main aim of creating economic added value for the community and as a tool for cultural preservation clearly empirical new approach.

Not only that, the choosing the appropriate area to create spaces for cultural tourism in the form of the floating market, which to create added economic value, community participation and self-sustainability for communities creating cultural added value and preserving local culture and way of life under the concept of sustainable cultural tourism. Therefore, there is an assessment of potential areas to support the creating spaces for cultural tourism in the form of floating market in the Sakon Nakhon Province, Thailand. Therefore, it was found that the most probable area was the area around Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand.

Nong Han is the largest natural freshwater lake in the northeast of Thailand and the second largest in Thailand. A resource should be conserved by the Cabinet on November 7, 1989 (B.E.2532). All the territory of Nong Han Lake covers an area of 77,014 acres or 123 square kilometers. Nong Han is located in Sakon Nakhon province.[2] With a characteristic geologic feature as a collapsed plain and became a swamp that supports the amount of water from 16 streams, making Nong Han an important wetland ecological system, which has outstanding characteristics of natural resources both physical and biological. Moreover; which is very important to the way of life and economy of the communities around Nong Han Who have lived in this pond for consumption throughout the ritual local traditions to promote tourism and various Thai traditional games.

Fig 1:-Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand (V.1) [3]

Fig 2:-Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand (V.2) [3]

Fig 3:-Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand (V.3) [4],[5]

Therefore, in order to know the feasibility of creating a floating market for spaces of cultural tourism to benefit in 3 dimensions: economically, socially and culturally, to the communities surrounding Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon Province in Thailand, and in response to the 12th (Thailand) National Economic and Social Development Plan (2017-2021), Strategy No. 3, creating economic strength and sustainable competitiveness. The development of the integrated tourism industry by promoting the creation of added value for tourism products and services by taking advantage of the Thai identity and identity that reflects the local culture and community way of life.[6] This will distribute income to people in the community and local people throughout the country. Including promoting tourism that takes into account the capacity to support the ecosystem in order to achieve balance and sustainability in the development of the Thai tourism industry. As well as developing man-made creative tourist attractions linked to tourism activities. As the reason mentioned above, the objective of this research is to study the feasibility of creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand.

II. METHOD

Data were collected from 400 purposive local residents which have gained residents surrounding the Nong Han Lake.

TABLE 1:- Reliability assessment

Reliability assessment of Questionnaire of the cultural tourism capacity of the creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept	Cronbach's Alpha
(1) Tourism attraction potential aspect	0.715
(2) Tourism support potential aspect	0.926
(3) Management aspect	0.718
Overall aspects	0.930

III. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH OUTCOMES

The result of research was the feasibility of creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand can be separated into 2 parts as following:

A. The First Part

The measuring the level opinion of local residents towards on the cultural tourism capacity of the creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept appears in Table 2. The result revealed that the local residents agreed with the creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon have cultural tourism capacity the overall average as whole as 3

The questions in the questionnaire were designed, which based upon the creating spaces for cultural tourism under the floating market concept. The questionnaire was revised to ensure construct validity and content validity by professors. Pilot study and reliability assessment were taken away from Cronbach α -coefficients that values of reliability coefficients for this research were all above 0.70 levels, which appeared in Table 1. Discriminant Power used Item-total Technique $0.05 r_{38} = 0.20$ [7], values within the range of 0.338- 0.750. The questionnaire consisted of a data regarding the cultural tourism capacity of the creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept in 3 aspects: (1) Tourism attraction potential consists of 2 sub-dimensions: (1.1) Art and cultural value and (1.2) Physical potential and activities, (2) Tourism support potential consists of 2 sub-dimensions as follows: (2.1) the potential to develop basic facilities and (2.2) the potential to develop tourism from external factors, and (3) management, consisting of 2 sub-dimensions: (3.1) tourism conservation management and (3.2) Tourism management. All of the items were measured by a five point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree), Then compare the rule of three in arithmetic of the local residents' opinion level analysis to examine the feasibility study of creating spaces for cultural tourism under the floating market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand.

aspects at a moderate level (Average = 3.441). With the local residents agreed with the creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon has cultural tourism capacity in the aspect of government agencies involved directly and indirectly can manage tourism as the first, and agree to a high level (Average = 3.690). (2) The local residents agreed with the creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon that has cultural tourism capacity in the aspect of tourism attractiveness as the second and agreed with the moderate level (Average = 3.543). And (3) the local residents agreed with the creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, which has cultural tourism capacity in the aspect of support tourism at a moderate level (Average = 3.090) as well.

TABLE 2:- The level opinion of local residents towards on the cultural tourism capacity of the creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept in overall aspects.

The level opinion of local residents towards on the cultural tourism capacity of the creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept in overall aspects	Average	SD.
1. Tourism attraction potential aspect	3.543	0.630
1.1 Art and cultural value	3.568	0.528
1.2 Physical potential and activities	3.517	0.709
2. Tourism support potential aspect	3.090	0.833
2.1 The potential to develop basic facilities	3.190	0.799
2.2 The potential to develop tourism from external factors	2.990	0.969
3. Management aspect	3.690	0.665
3.1 Tourism conservation management	3.570	0.583
3.2 Tourism management	3.810	0.665
Overall aspects	3.441	0.617

Remark

Average	4.51 – 5.00	Very high level
Average	3.51 – 4.50	High level
Average	2.51 – 3.50	Moderate level
Average	1.51 – 2.50	low level
Average	1.00 – 1.50	Very low level

The raw score prediction equation $X = \frac{(3.441 \times 100)}{5.000}$

X = 68.82%

Fig 4:- The level opinion of local residents towards on the cultural tourism capacity of the creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept in overall aspects.

B. The Second Part

Compare the rule of three in arithmetic of the local residents' opinion level analysis to test the feasibility of creating spaces for cultural tourism under the floating market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand which appeared hypotheses as the following.

H₀: Infeasibility of creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand ($X < 80\%$).

H₁: Feasibility of creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand ($X \geq 80\%$).

Which could predict the feasibility of creating spaces for cultural tourism under the floating market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand by calculate the raw score prediction equation as the following:

The result revealed that rejected the alternative hypothesis (H₁), which identified the Infeasibility of creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand. Due to the result of calculating is $X = 68.82\%$ that value less than 80% as criteria that identified in hypothesis the mentioned above.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The finding of this research is shown that there is infeasibility of creating spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand. Even though the local residents which have gained residents surrounding the Nong Han Lake agreed with this idea as a moderate level overall opinion. This may be due to the fact that there are still many issues that need to be developed, especially in terms of tourism support.

When considering the results of the data analysis, it was found that around Nong Han Lake, there is no systematic parking management and safety for tourists. Public toilets for tourism need to be developed to be ready to accommodate all types of tourists. As well as having to develop clearly in tourism from external factors. Local authorities are also unable to provide support for the development of basic facilities. Providing assistance in public relations related and providing support for the conservation of landscape architecture as appropriate. In addition, there must be a unit to determine the appropriate point coordinates to create spaces for cultural tourism under the Floating Market concept at the Nong Han Lake, Sakon Nakhon, Thailand. And it is of great importance that environmental and sustainability impacts are assessed in the construction of a concrete cultural tourism space; moreover, must be social and economic impact assessment.

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